

Electrode Kinetics and Formation Constants of Mixed Complexes

K. D. GUPTA, K. K. CHOUDHARY and J. N. GAUR

Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 10 May 1977, revised 24 February 1978, accepted 3 March 1978

Attempts have been made for the determination of kinetic parameters of mixed system of zinc with 1 : 2 propane diamine and 1 : 3 propane diamine keeping the concentration of the weaker ligand 1 : 3 propane diamine constant and varying the stronger ligand 1 : 2 propane diamine. The reduction process is found to be quasi-reversible and diffusion controlled.

VARIOUS methods have been developed to determine kinetic parameters. The first theoretical treatment of polarographic current voltage curves was attempted by Heyrovsky and Ilkovic¹. Later the various methods developed to determine K_s (rate constant) and α are due to Neiman², Koutecky³, Delahy⁴, Kivolo and Oldham⁵, Tamamushi and Tanaka⁶, Tachi⁷, Matsuda⁸, Randles⁹, Stromberg¹⁰ and Sathyanarayana¹¹ etc.

Attempts have been made by a number of workers¹²⁻¹³, for the determination of kinetic parameters in case of simple system of zinc with formate, citrate, acetate, tartrate but no attempt has been made so far in the determination of kinetic parameters for mixed complexes of zinc.

Therefore, we have made an attempt for the first time for the determination of kinetic parameters of mixed system of zinc with 1 : 2 propanediamine and 1 : 3 propanediamine. Here in mixed system the concentration of weaker ligand (1 : 3 propanediamine) is kept constant while that of stronger 1 : 2 propanediamine varied. The overall formation constants of mixed complexes have been determined by Schaap and McMasters method¹⁴. The present study is in succession to the mixed complex study made by us¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Theory :

The DeFord and Hume's treatment for simple complexes developed by Schaap and McMasters for mixed complexes gives a new function $F_{00}(X, Y)$

$$F_{00}(X, Y) = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{.435nF}{RT} E_{\frac{1}{2}} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_c} \right]$$

where various symbols have their usual significance. In Ledan's approach where the metal ion forms two complexes with ease of the ligand may be written as

$$F_{00}(X, Y) = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01}[Y] + \beta_{02}[Y]^2 + \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[Y, X] + \beta_{20}[X]^2$$

or

$$F_{00}(X, Y) = A + B[X] + C[X]^2$$

where $A = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01}[Y] + \beta_{02}[Y]^2$

$$B = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[Y]$$

and $C = \beta_{20}$

In practice the concentration of weak ligand is maintained constant while that of stronger is varied, the original graphical method may be extended to F_{00} data. The intercept on F_{00} axis gives the value of A so that

$$F_{10} = \frac{F_{00} - A}{[X]} = B + C[X]$$

a similar plotting F_{10} vs X and taking the intercept on F_{10} axis as B

$$F_{20} = \frac{F_{10} - B}{[X]} = C$$

From the knowledge of B we can compute the value of β_{11} (mixed complex formation constant).

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used during all the experimental procedure. Solution of Zn^{2+} was prepared by weighing zinc nitrate and standardised as usual. Solutions of 1 : 2 propanediamine and 1 : 3 propanediamine were used as complexing agent. The ionic strength was kept constant at 1.5M by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. Titron X-100 was used as maximum suppressor.

The polarograms were taken manually in a H type cell saturated with NaCl agar-agar bridge. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics : $m = 2.16$ mg/sec, $t = 4.6$ sec (in open circuit). The temperature was kept constant at

30±0.1° with the help of Haake type ultra thermostat. Purified nitrogen was used for deaeration.

Results and Discussion

Solutions containing 0.5 mM Zn²⁺ and various concentrations of 1 : 2 propanediamine (.01, .02,08M) were prepared at fixed concentration of 1 : 3 propanediamine (.02M). Requisite amount of sodium perchlorate was added to keep constant ionic strength (u=1.5M). In each case a single well defined reduction wave appeared whose half-wave potential was found to shift towards more negative side and diffusion current decreased with increasing concentration of propylenediamine. The above results indicate mixed ligand complex formation between 1 : 3 propanediamine and 1 : 2 propanediamine with zinc.

The plots of i_d vs h (h is effective height of mercury column after applying back pressure and i_d vs C (concentration of the ligand) come to be linear confirming the system to be diffusion controlled.

Further the plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs E_{de} were linear with slope of the order of 37±2mV indicating the system to be quasi-reversible. Hence $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}^r$ reversible half-wave potentials were determined by Gellings¹⁸ method which involves the plots of

$$\left[E + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{i}{i_d - i} \right] \text{ vs } i \text{ at zero current value.}$$

As the electrode process is quasi-reversible, the kinetic parameters were determined by Gellings method which involve

$$\log (Z - 1) = n \frac{1.13}{t} - (1 - \alpha)$$

$$\text{where } Z = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{nF}{2.303RT} (E_{\frac{1}{2}}^r - E) - \log \left(\frac{i}{i_d - i} \right) \right]$$

$$\text{and } \xi = \frac{nF}{RT} (E - E_{\frac{1}{2}}^r)$$

from the slope and intercept of the $\log (Z - 1)$ against $(E - E_{\frac{1}{2}}^r)$. The values of α and or K_s determined and the results have been summarised in Table 1.

The value of K_s was found to be of the order of 10⁻⁴ cm/sec, which confirms that the reduction process is quasi-reversible and from the table it is clear that irreversibility is increased in the presence of ligand 1 : 3 propanediamine in comparison to that of simple zinc ($K_s \times 10^3 = 4.42$ cm/sec).

In case of mixed system the values of K_s was found to be of the same order but decrease at

varying concentration of the stronger ligand (1 : 2 propanediamine) showing that stronger ligand favours reversibility. The values are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Kinetic Parameters for Zn ²⁺ 1 : 3 Propanediamine System			
C _z (moles)	D ^{1/2} × 10 ⁴ (cm ² /sec)	λ	K _s × 10 ⁴ (cm/sec)
0.01	3.3	0.3549	1.17
0.02	7.6	0.7764	2.19
0.03	9.59	0.9590	2.5
Kinetic Parameters for mixed complex Zn 1 : 2 Propanediamine- 1 : 3 Propanediamine System 1 : 3 Propanediamine = .02m fixed.			
0.01	2.5	0.9335	2.5
0.05	2.45	2.042	5.0
0.07	2.54	3.715	9.4

Simple Complexes :

The reduction of Zn²⁺ in the medium of 1 : 2 propanediamine 1 : 3 propanediamine separately was found irreversible and diffusion controlled slope as evident from the constant value $i_d/h^{\frac{1}{2}}_{err}$. Conventional logarithmic plots yield good straight lines but the resulting slopes were found not to be in agreement with theoretical values for reversible process thus indicating irreversible nature of the reduction process.

Overall formation of the simple complexes were determined by DeFord and Hume's¹⁹ method using the polarographic measurement. The results are summarised below :

Simple species	Overall formation constant
[Zn (1 : 3 propanediamine)] ²⁺ log β ₀₁	12.6990
[Zn (1 : 3 propanediamine)] ²⁺ log β ₀₂	14.00
[Zn (1 : 2 propanediamine)] ²⁺ log β ₁₀	12.6021
[Zn (1 : 2 propanediamine)] ₂ ²⁺ log β ₂₀	15.00

Mixed Complex :

The nature of reduction of Zn²⁺ in the mixed medium was the same as in individual media. The Schaap and McMasters function F₀₀ was calculated over the given range of variable concentration of 1 : 2 propanediamine at one fixed concentration of 1 : 3 propanediamine.

F₀₀ function and other function values along with the polarographic measurement were recorded in Table 2 at 30°. The values of B.C. as a result of graphical extrapolation are also mentioned in the table. The value of A calculated in theory.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC MEASUREMENTS AND F_{11} FUNCTIONS OF $Zn(II)$ 1 : 2 PROPANEDIAMINE-1 : 3 PROPANEDIAMINE SYSTEM AT 30°C [1 : 3 PROPANEDIAMINE]=0.02M FIXED i_d OF SIMPLE METAL ION=90 div.

$-E_{1/2}^r$ OF SIMPLE METAL ION=0.98,0 VOLTS

C_x (in moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ V vs S.C.E.	i_d (div)	$F_{00} \times 10^{-11}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-12}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-16}$
0.00	0.9840	90	—	—	—
0.01	1.3405	86	7.9	60.0	—
0.02	1.3555	85	25.59	12.0	2.75
0.03	1.3650	84	53.67	17.3	3.61
0.04	1.3700	81	79.75	19.5	3.25
0.05	1.3750	80	119.80	23.6	3.42
0.06	1.3805	79	180.70	29.8	3.88
0.07	1.3820	78	205.20	29.1	3.22
0.08	1.3850	79	265.00	88.0	3.31

$A = 1.4 \times 10^{11}$, $B = 60 \times 10^{12}$, $C = 3.5 \times 10^{16}$,
 $\beta_{11} = 3.0 \times 10^{16}$

Using the value of B at .02M fixed, concentration of 1 : 3 propanediamine, the value of β_{11} is calculated by the equation

$$B = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}(Y)$$

Discussion

The structures of 1 : 2 propanediamine and 1 : 3 propanediamine respectively are

From the structures it is seen that 1 : 2 propanediamine is a stronger ligand than 1 : 3 propanediamine, which is also observed by our results of overall formation constants and supported by mixed complex formation.

Scheme

In the scheme numerical values are log K values where K is the equilibrium constant of the corresponding step. X and Y stand for 1 : 2 propanediamine and 1 : 3 propanediamine respectively.

It is seen from the scheme that $[Zn(Y)]^{2+}$ can add to X more easily than $[Zn(X)]^{2+}$ to [Y] and also that the tendency of $[Zn(Y)_2]^{2+}$ to add [X] is more than to add [Y]. In the same way all the above results show that approach of [X] to the metal ion is less hindered than the approach of [Y]. And also [X] forms stronger complexes than [Y] with Zn^{2+} .

Since the complexes of Zn^{2+} with 1 : 2 propanediamine and 1 : 3 propanediamine are very much stable, they can effect the system wherever they are likely to be formed. Since the reduction of zinc is diffusion controlled, it can be estimated in the presence of 1 : 2 propanediamine and 1 : 3 propanediamine polarographically.

References

- J. HEVROVSKY and D. ILKOVIC, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, **21**, 836.
- N. N. NEIMAN, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1948, **32**, 1954.
- J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZECH, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, **21**, 836.
- P. DELAHY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1430.
- P. KIVOLO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4142.
- R. TAMANUSHI and N. TANAKA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1949, **22**, 187, 227 and 1950, **23**, 1160.
- I. TACHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **28**, 423.
- H. MATSUDA and Y. AYABE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1955, **23**, 423 and 1959, **36**, 1164.
- J. E. B. RANGLES, *Can. J. Chem.* 1959, **37**, 238.
- A. G. STROMBERG, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1962, **36**, 2714.
- S. SATHYANARAYANA, *J. Electroanal.* 1964, **7**, 403.
- H. MATSUDA, *Z. Electrochem.* 1961, **65**, 489 ; 1958, **62**, 977.
- H. MATSUDA and Y. AYABE, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1959, **63**, 1164.
- W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. McMASTERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.
- K. K. CHOUDHARY, S. C. BAGHEL and J. N. GAUR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1977, **50**, 243.
- K. K. CHOUDHARY, S. C. BAGHEL and J. N. GAUR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2513-2516.
- K. D. GUPTA, S. C. BAGHEL, K. K. CHOUDHURY and J. N. GAUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1977, **54**, 833.
- P. J. GELLINGS, *Z. Electrochem. Ber. Bunsenger Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 477, 481, 799 ; 1963, **67**, 167.
- D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.